

Synthesis and analytical application of 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-(4-sulphonamidophenyl)triazene in the spectrophotometric determination of copper(II)

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3-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1-(4-sulphonamidophenyl)triazene (HMST) has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II}. The light brown coloured complex absorbs at 360 nm at pH 6.7–7.3. The validity of Beer's law for this 1 : 2 (Cu : R) complex has been verified. Stability constants (log β) have been found to be 9.83 and 9.31 by two different methods, respectively. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 6158 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 10.31 ng cm⁻².

In continuation of our earlier studies¹ the present communication reports the results of spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) with 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-(4-sulphonamidophenyl)triazene (HMST). The present communication is the first report regarding utility of sulphonamide based hydroxytriazenes for spectrophotometric determination of copper.

Results and discussion

On the basis of studies of molar composition it is found that copper(II) form 1 : 2 complex with HMST.

Harvey and Manning's² method and Purohit's³ method have been used to determine the stability constants. The values of stability constant obtained by two different methods were 9.83 and 9.31 respectively, which agree well. Further, the precision studies considering ten values of absorbance gave a precision of 0.040 ppm of Cu^{II}. Thus, it can be concluded that the reagent HMST can be used for the spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II}.

Interference studies : Interference of number of cations and anions on the absorbance of Cu^{II}-HMST complex was studied at equivalent, five-fold and ten-fold concentration of interfering ions, respectively. The ions which interfered at one of the three levels was not screened further, whereas those which did not interfere at equivalent concentration or more were further screened at higher concentration. It was observed that even in presence of ten-fold concentration i.e. 100 ppm of Cl⁻, Br⁻, CH₃COO⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₂⁻, F⁻, NO₃⁻, Hg²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mn²⁺, Pb²⁺ and Mg²⁺ there was no interference, whereas at 50 ppm, Ba²⁺, Sn²⁺, Cr³⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Ni²⁺ interfered in the determination. At equivalent concentration i.e. 10 ppm, the determination could be done in

presence of 24 cation/anions viz., Cl⁻, Br⁻, CH₃COO⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, C₂O₄²⁻, I⁻, NO₂⁻, F⁻, NO₃⁻, Hg²⁺, NH₄⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mn²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cr³⁺, Cd²⁺, Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Ni²⁺. Thus it is indicated that 10 ppm of Cu^{II} can be determined in presence of several cations and anions with the reagent HMST successfully.

Synthesis of the ligand : HMST was synthesized by coupling methyl hydroxylamine with diazotized sulphanilamide at 0°. The steps of preparation are described as follows :

(a) **Preparation of methylhydroxylamine :** Nitromethane (0.3 M), 30 g, of NH₄Cl and 250 ml water were mixed and stirred mechanically. 40 g of Zn dust was added in small portions, such that temperature did not go beyond 45–60°. Addition of Zn dust was completed in 90 min. The reaction mixture was stirred mechanically for 15 more min, filtered under suction and a washing was given with ice cold water. The filtrate was taken in one litre beaker and kept in freezer at about 0° and used as such for coupling.

(b) **Diazotization of sulphanilamide :** In a 500 ml beaker, 0.2 mole of sulphanilamide were dissolved in warm mixture of 50 ml concentrated HCl and 50 ml of water. After stirring vigorously the mixture was kept in the freezer to cool. In another beaker 13.9 g of sodium nitrite was dissolved in 40 ml distilled water and it was kept in freezer for cooling. The beaker which contained sulfanilamide solution was put in an ice bath to maintain temperature between 0 to 5°. To this sodium nitrite solution was added drop by drop with continuous stirring. The diazotized product so obtained was directly used for coupling.

(c) **Coupling :** The methylhydroxylamine prepared in step (a) was taken out of the freezer and kept in an ice

Note

bath, then it was mechanically stirred. The temperature of diazotized product obtained in step (b) was also maintained between 0 to 5° and it was added drop by drop to hydroxylamine solution. Occasionally sodium acetate solution (10%) was added to maintain pH between 5 to 6. When the addition of diazonium salt was complete the mixture was stirred for another 15 min and the resultant mixture was filtered under suction. The residue was washed with ice cold water. This reaction resulted in the formation of hydroxytriazene.

The crude compound so obtained was repeatedly crystallized from ethanol in the presence of activated charcoal, white shining crystals, m.p. 153° were obtained as final product. The compound was duly characterized by IR and CHN analysis.

Stock solution :

⇒ *Metal solution :* The stock solution of copper(II) $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was prepared by dissolving required quantity of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ in nitric acid. It was made upto mark by double-distilled water. The stock solution was standardized iodometrically. The solutions of lower concentration were prepared by dilution of stock solution.

Reagent solution : The stock solution of reagent ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of reagent in ethanol. The stock solution was further diluted to appropriate dilution as and when required.

Solution for pH adjustment.

Tris buffer : An aqueous solution of 1% tris(hydroxymethyl)amino methane was prepared in double-distilled water. The solution was used to maintain the pH.

Instruments : The spectrophotometric work was carried out on 108-Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometer, for pH measurement Systronic 324 pH meter was used.

References

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